

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF PRACTICAL LINGUISTICS

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются актуальные проблемы практической лингвистики, охарактеризованы вопросы, касающиеся использования языка в различных сферах жизни. Был проведен анализ фактов, посвященных языковой адаптации. Показано, что адаптация требует глубокого понимания как исходного, так и целевого культурного контекста. Обращено внимание на широкий спектр вопросов, касающихся актуальных проблем практической лингвистики.

Ключевые слова: практическая лингвистика, языковая ситуация, сферы жизни, культурный контекст, клиентский опыт в переводе, эффективная и своевременная коммуникация, междисциплинарный подход.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada amaliy tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolari muhokama qilinadi va hayotning turli sohalarida tildan foydalanish bilan bog'liq masalalar yoritiladi. Tilning moslashuvi bo'yicha faktlar tahlili o'tkazildi. Moslashuv manba va maqsadli madaniy kontekstni chuqur tushunishni talab qilishi ko'rsatilgan. Amaliy tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolari bilan bog'liq keng ko'lamli masalalarga e'tibor qaratiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: amaliy tilshunoslik, til vaziyati, hayot sohaları, madaniy kontekst, tarjimada mijoz tajribasi, samarali va o'z vaqtida muloqot, fanlararo yondashuv.

Annotation: This article discusses current problems of practical linguistics and describes issues related to the use of language in various spheres of life. An analysis of the facts on language adaptation was carried out. It is shown that adaptation requires a deep understanding of both the source and target cultural context. Attention is drawn to a wide range of issues related to current problems of practical linguistics.

Key words: practical linguistics, language situation, spheres of life, cultural context, client experience in translation, effective and timely communication, interdisciplinary approach.

Current problems of practical linguistics cover a wide range of issues relating to the use of language in various spheres of life.

First of all, it is language adaptation, how to effectively adapt texts for different cultural and linguistic contexts, especially in the context of globalization. Language adaptation is the process of changing text or speech to make it more understandable and acceptable to the target audience, taking into account cultural, social and linguistic

characteristics. This process plays a key role in various fields such as translation, marketing, education and intercultural communication. Here you need to consider taking into account the cultural norms, traditions and customs of the target audience [1:34]. For example, some expressions or jokes may be incomprehensible or even offensive in another cult. If we talk about lexical adaptation, then we need to mention a change in vocabulary for better perception.

This may include using simpler words or equivalents that resonate better with the reader. Syntactic adaptation is important, changing sentence structure to ensure clarity. For example, some languages prefer shorter sentences. Customize your writing style based on your audience. For example, scientific texts require a formal style, while a more informal and conversational style may be appropriate for a youth audience. Taking into account the specifics of the situation in which the adapted text will be used, for example, advertising, educational materials or publications on social networks. Applying adapted texts in a real situation and collecting feedback from the target audience for further improvement [3:18]. Adaptation requires a deep understanding of both the source and target cultural context. Changes may cause some nuances and meanings to be lost. Different audiences may interpret adapted texts differently.

In conclusion, language adaptation is an important tool to overcome language and cultural barriers, which is especially important in today's globalized world.

Secondly, there is the customer experience in translation: the study of how to improve the quality of translation and make it more understandable to the target audience. Customer experience in translation is the totality of customer experiences and interactions with translation services throughout the entire process. The importance of this aspect lies in the fact that customer satisfaction directly affects the reputation of translation agencies and further cooperation. Let's look at the key elements and factors influencing the customer experience in translation. The quality of the translation is a critical factor. Clients expect precision, naturalness and stylistic compliance. It is important to attract qualified translators who not only speak the language but are also familiar with the topic of translation. Effective and timely communication between the

client and the translator or agency improves the client experience. Feedback on progress, possible problems and deadlines is important.

Customer experience in translation is a complex process that requires attention to many details [2:41]. A successful translation agency should strive not only for high quality translations, but also to create a positive and memorable experience for its clients. This not only builds trust, but also increases the likelihood of repeat business and referrals.

In addition to the above, current problems in practical linguistics cover a wide range of issues, such as cognitive linguistics (understanding how people perceive and process linguistic information, and how this affects language learning and use), cross-cultural communication (problems related to differences in the linguistic and cultural context, which may lead to misunderstandings, technology and automation (the impact of new technologies such as machine translation and natural language processing on the practical application of linguistic knowledge, language and identity (how language influences the formation of personal and group identity, especially in multilingual communities), social aspects of language (language policy issues, linguistic equality and protection of endangered languages), phonetic and phonological changes (the study of changes in pronunciation and their consequences for communication).

These problems require an interdisciplinary approach and can be solved through the collaboration of linguists, psychologists, cultural scientists and communication specialists.

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